

UNIVERSITY
of HULL

Energy &
Environment Institute

DIG Annual Monitoring Summary

2023/2024

City of
Doncaster
Council

NORTH
EAST
LINCOLNSHIRE
COUNCIL

Flood and coastal resilience innovation programme
Part of the 1000
Flood and coastal innovation programmes

Document Control

Document:	DIG Annual Monitoring Summary 2023/2024
Project:	F-NEL014-5-DIG - SuDS Monitoring
Client:	Doncaster, Immingham and Grimsby (DIG) Surface Water Resilience Project
File Location:	Https://Hullacuk.Sharepoint.Com/Sites/Inssudslabuk-Team/Shared Documents/DIG- Suds Monitoring/00_General/Year Review/DIG_Year_Report_23_24_P2.0.Docx

Revision:	P01	Prepared by:	AO
Date:	09/12/2024	Checked by:	SJM

Description:	DIG Annual Monitoring Summary 2023/2024
--------------	---

Cite as:

Osborne, Wm. A.* & Stuart J. McLelland (2025). *DIG Annual Monitoring Summary 2023/2024*. University of Hull.

Acknowledgement:

This work was funded through the UK government’s Flood and Coastal Resilience Innovation Programme (FCRIP), which is part of the government’s National Flood and Coastal Erosion Risk Management Strategy for England. FCRIP is funded by Defra and managed by the Environment Agency.

Preface

The hydrological year from 1st October 2023 to 30th September 2024 has been utilised for the annual summary of SuDS monitoring within the DIG project. This summary includes rainfall amounts and their implications for natural soil moisture and conductivity, as well as data on Wybers Wood Pond and the SuDS downpipe interventions.

Wherever possible, a full year's worth of data has been included; however, the downpipe interventions were only installed between November 2023 and June 2024. Consequently, the data presented reflects the period during which these interventions have been active.

Periods of maintenance or downtime are also reflected in the data, resulting from either the school's internet being non-operational or sensors becoming blocked or needing rebooting. Instances of these occurrences are documented within the summary.

Year in review

The milestones for the monitoring programme of the DIG project are highlighted below:

In the 2023/24 hydrological year, individual asset SuDS monitoring commenced with the initial monitoring of downpipe intervention planters towards the end of 2023. Prior monitoring of SuDS was conducted at Wybers Wood Academy, with sewer monitoring concluding in Autumn 2023 and the results thereof found within the end of sewer monitoring report already supplied.

The most significant addition to the project was the completion of the Broadway rain gardens, which feature six new nodes capable of measuring up to 500 parameters, including the depth of water in sewers and the lateral movement of water across the rain gardens. These SuDS can then be shown to either have an impact or not through the restarting of monitoring of the sewer system in the area. Due to only coming online Summer 2024, they are not included in this report.

This year, downpipe interventions featuring SuDS planters were completed, with all consortium areas fitted with monitoring systems. Trials were conducted using a flow meter on the downpipes, providing valuable insights into the challenges faced, such as blockages caused by debris in gutters or wind interference within the pipes. It is now clear that specific adaptations are necessary to improve performance, including the installation of filters and caps on the pipes to mitigate these issues.

The first mobile operated gateway was installed at Oasis Academy ending a yearlong attempt to allow school network access. At a cost of £400 a localised Wi-Fi network was created which has allowed data to be collected from the area.

During this period, the data portal for displaying all real-time data was launched, receiving 30,000 hits on the webpage since its inception. The start of the Water Data for People project has also allowed weather station reports to be given to schools with their own dedicated school zones.

Rainfall

Weather stations have been operational since before October 2023, marking the first full hydrological year of observation. In addition to the localised rain gauge (blue), meniscus radar data has also been included for this time period to facilitate comparison (yellow). A monthly climate average for the 30-year period from 1991 to 2020, as supplied by the Met Office, is also presented (orange). The monthly totals are located within the bar charts themselves. A table at the end of the rainfall sections shows the totals for each station and a comparison against the Standard Annual Average Rainfall (SAAR) SAAR6190.

A residual plot is also created between the observed rainfall and the radar data. It compares against the times in which either both observed and radar measured at the same time, or if one and not the other recorded. It does not include when both measured zero as that would skew the results. It also considers periods in which there were blockages and rainfall errors within the data.

Scawthorpe (Castle Hills) Rainfall

Scawthorpe experienced a wetter than average year, with up to 36% more rainfall compared to the climate average, and 33% more than the Standard Annual Average Rainfall (SAAR) recorded by the rain gauge. The radar measured rainfall was significantly higher, exceeding the recorded value by 18%, which is approximately 66% above the climate average. Consequently, the 2023/24 year was wetter than average overall.

The residual plot determines that there was ~ 26% of the time when the observed and radar rainfall matched, while there was ~30% more likely to overestimate rainfall than underestimate it the rest of the time.

Clay Lane (Hungerhill) Rainfall

The weather station was offline for June due to maintenance at the outbuilding at the school. No comparison between annual rainfall amounts can be used due to this.

Clay Lane experienced a wetter than average year, with October, December, and April being particularly wet, receiving up to twice the typical rainfall. Based on radar measurements, the year was 57% wetter than the expected climate average. The nearest Environment Agency (EA) rain gauge recorded 776.7 mm of rainfall during this period, including 29.4 mm in June. Adding the recorded on-site rainfall brings the total to 817.4 mm, which is comparable to the rainfall at Scawthorpe for the same period.

The comparison between observed and radar measurements show around 32% agreement between them, with again radar overestimating rainfall 47% of the time or underestimating 20% of the time.

Immingham (Pilgrim Academy) Rainfall

*May rainfall lower than expected due to blockage in the rain gauge from spiders.
August Rainfall misses out the last 5 days due to the network being disconnected for the remainder of the hydrological year.*

Pilgrim Academy followed the same trend of the 2023/24 year being wetter than average. However, due to incomplete data, direct comparisons with average annual rainfall cannot be made. The nearest Environment Agency (EA) gauge recorded an annual rainfall of 822.4 mm, and estimating the missing months brings the total recorded value to approximately 762 mm.

Agreement between radar and observed was ~24% for the monitoring period, with overestimation by the radar for around half of the rainfall measured.

Oasis Weather station only active for September

With only a comparison to the radar rainfall, the year has been wetter on average apart from June and August with ~37% more rainfall than the climate average.

Broadway (Western Primary) Rainfall

Broadway has a complete hydrological year of data, with no missing information. The recorded rainfall is 42% higher than the climate average for the area and 36% above the Standard Annual Average Rainfall (SAAR). The recorded rainfall and radar measurements are almost identical, with only a ~7 mm difference for the year.

Radar measurements continue to overestimate according to the observed rainfall measured in this period. Around a third of the time the results matched.

Wybers Wood (Wybers Wood Academy) Rainfall

Wybers Wood's total recorded rainfall was significantly lower than Broadway's, despite being less than 2 km apart. It recorded 17% less rainfall than Broadway but was still 20% above the climate average. The radar-measured total for Wybers Wood was lower than Broadway's but approximately 11% higher than the recorded rainfall for the year.

Residuals for Wybers Wood shows that there is around a third of the time when observed and radar rainfall matched. There was less underestimation of rainfall but were some substantial overestimation by up to 2 mm within a 5 minute period.

Location	Recorded Annual Rainfall (mm)	Radar Annual Rainfall (mm)	Climate Average Annual Rainfall (mm)	FEH Standard Annual Average Rainfall SAAR6190 (mm)
Scawthorpe	793.6	939.2	581.9	595
Clay Lane	Incomplete Dataset (EA – 776.8)	911.5	581.9	583
Immingham-Pilgrim Academy	Incomplete Dataset (EA – 822.4)	825.2	600.9	616
Immingham-Oasis Academy	Incomplete Dataset (EA – 822.4)	825.2	600.9	618
Broadway	854.2	847.6	600.9	625
Wybers Wood	718.4	813.2	600.9	619

The discrepancies between observed and radar-measured rainfall were generally subtle, with occasional instances of 0.2 mm being recorded when no rain actually fell. However, there were also instances of substantial overestimations of rainfall by the radar compared to the actual measurements. Comparisons with EA rain gauges nearby also appear to agree closer with the observed rainfall over the radar.

There is somewhat confidence in using radar measurements when observed rainfall is unavailable, but rainfall intensities and rainfall accumulations might be marginally off which that fell.

Natural Soil – Soil Moisture

Soil moisture is an indicator of the health and functionality of ecosystems, influencing the capacity of the soil to retain water and how far it infiltrates. It is recorded as a relative percentage, reflecting the amount of water present in the soil compared to its total capacity.

In our observations, the maximum percentage of soil moisture recorded is 55%. This figure is significant as it indicates the soil's saturation level, where the soil can hold water without becoming waterlogged.

Soil moisture probes were situated in representative areas of 'natural' ground close to weather station (apart from Oasis due to concrete foundations). These record moisture at 10 cm intervals down the probe.

The first plot represents the actual soil moisture readings that have been recorded while the second is a heatmap of the deviation from the annual average.

Scawthorpe (Castle Hills) Natural Soil Moisture

Data started from December 2023 after relocation of probe. Intermittent drop outs of probe in February and September due to battery replacement required.

Rainfall was observed to increase soil moisture at all depths down to 60 cm, with the 10-20 cm horizons being the most responsive. The soil's ability to react to water even at 60 cm suggests a high level of transmissivity. Looking at deviations from the annual average, the cool blue and green colours indicate minimal sustained change from the norm, with summer possibly being ~5% drier across the soil profile.

In terms of SuDS installations in the area, the ground does have the capacity to allow infiltration. However, the relatively static annual soil moisture retention could present challenges during wetter periods.

Clay Lane (Hungerhill) Natural Soil Moisture

Power issues around February and then no internet access in June for missing data.

The natural ground at this location was assumed to be made ground due to its proximity to built-up areas. However, the data shows that the top 30 cm is receptive to rainfall, with soil moisture reaching a maximum of ~35%, which is relatively comparable to Scawthorpe for clay-type soils. At the 50-60 cm depth, soil moisture changes are less pronounced, showing a more gradual increase in winter and decrease in summer. The top 10 cm displays the most significant variations from the annual average, as indicated by bright blue peaks in the heatmap, while other layers show only ~5% deviation. During summer, the entire soil column visibly dries out, with a deviation of around 10%.

Although no SuDS installations are planned directly at this site, any other ground that has been 'made' may exhibit different behaviour.

Immingham (Pilgrim Academy) Soil Moisture

Data after 23rd August missing due to IT issues at the school.

Compared to other natural soils monitored in the project, Pilgrim exhibits a very flashy response in the top 10 cm, frequently reaching nearly 50% soil moisture, which would indicate a highly waterlogged state or even standing water at times. This flashy response is less evident in the lower levels, with the deepest layer at 60 cm showing negligible change throughout the year, as highlighted by the 0% deviation from the annual average. The flashy behaviour can also be observed extending into the 20 cm horizon, with bright blue lines indicating deviation. A drying period is visible, spreading downwards from July onwards.

In terms of SuDS potential at this location, soils with similar properties would likely struggle to infiltrate below 50 cm, as the soil remains saturated (though water can still percolate). The sharp flashy response to rainfall events would likely lead to surface flooding and increased runoff in this area.

Broadway (Western Primary) Soil Moisture

Period of loss of data in March due to resetting of node.

Broadway's soil maintains high moisture levels across all horizons for over half of the year, with capacity only beginning to build after May. The 50-60 cm horizon shows no deviation from the average during this period, with only a slight ~3% decrease in moisture during the summer. The top 10-20 cm horizons exhibit a flashy response to rainfall, though they do not reach full saturation, making surface water unlikely. The drying front in the soil starts in July, gradually extending to the deepest horizons. A reduction in infiltration capacity due to drying is evident, with the soil remaining quite dry even into late September.

The local soil is heavy clay, which retains moisture for long periods but also takes time to rehydrate once dried out. Given the drier conditions for the soil this year, it is anticipated that the recovery period for the soil to begin absorbing water will be prolonged, increasing the likelihood of runoff as we approach winter 2024.

Wybers Wood (Wybers Wood Academy) Soil Moisture

IT issue in June. 10 cm horizon no data due to soil contraction until September rain.

The Wybers Wood soil probe is located near a pond, which may have some impact on the soil. The 50-60 cm horizon remained constantly saturated until August, when it began to dry out, roughly corresponding to the level of the pond base, followed by a rapid drying period with more than a 20% deviation from the average. The top 10 cm is highly responsive to both rain and drying, showing the most intense deviations. The deeper horizons remained relatively stable with negligible changes throughout the year, only drying out in July. While the soil properties here are similar to those at Broadway, Wybers Wood exhibits a much flashier response in the top 10 cm. This could be due to plant growth, as Broadway has cut grass, whereas Wybers Wood has shrubby vegetation, which likely led to a greater draw of water from May onwards as the plants started growing. For SuDS in this location, additional storage or soil replacement would be necessary to provide adequate water storage, potentially utilising features like the pond.

Natural Soil – Soil Conductivity

Electrical conductivity (EC) in the context of the TriSCAN system used with DIG refers to the ability of a solution, specifically soil water, to conduct electricity, which is directly related to the concentration of soluble salts (ions) in the solution. Conductivity is influenced by the types of ions present, their concentrations, and the temperature of the solution. The TriSCAN uses sensors to measure changes in soil water content and salinity, providing a Volumetric Ion Content (VIC) output. While VIC is not a direct measure of EC, it reflects changes in salinity, and a relationship between VIC and EC can be established through calibration specific to soil types.

Monitoring EC helps to understand the accumulation and leaching of salts in the soil, which can impact drainage efficiency and plant growth. In SuDS applications, managing the salinity and soil water content is crucial to ensure that drainage systems are not only effective in water management but also prevent environmental issues like soil degradation or contamination of nearby water bodies with excess salts.

Real-time monitoring of EC through systems like TriSCAN can be used to track how efficiently SuDS installations, such as permeable pavements, swales, or infiltration trenches, are managing water flow and salt movement. This data can guide interventions to improve soil structure, manage leaching, and optimise the system for both flood prevention and soil health, making SuDS more effective in sustainable water and salinity management.

Using natural soil as a control to SuDS will highlight the differences between natural runoff and from urban runoff.

The first plot represents the actual soil conductivity readings that have been recorded while the second is a heatmap of the deviation from the annual average.

Scawthorpe (Castle Hills) Soil Conductivity

Scawthorpe’s soil conductivity remains very stable throughout the year across the soil profile, with only around a 10% deviation from the average. This consistency can be attributed to its location, which doesn’t experience runoff from surfaces and is situated in a more natural area of the playground, factors that influence the relatively constant soil conductivity measurements.

Clay Lane (Hungerhill) Soil Moisture

In comparison to Scawthorpe, which shows stable soil conductivity with only a 10% deviation throughout the year, Clay Lane exhibits small perturbations in the top 20 cm of the soil. Conductivity decreases during winter, likely due to rainwater dilution, while it increases in summer as water loss concentrates the ions. Given the location, it is unlikely that any external sources of ions are affecting the soil. However, sharper rises in soil conductivity in the top 20 cm could pose a risk to plant life if the levels remain elevated for extended periods.

Immingham (Pilgrim Academy) Soil Conductivity

Soil conductivity at Pilgrim Academy is similar to that at Clay Lane, with conductivity increasing as summer approaches. However, this is only observed in the top 10 cm, while the lower horizons show a decrease. This, in conjunction with recorded soil moisture, may suggest that capillary action is drawing water upwards into the drier soils from a cleaner source of water.

Broadway (Western Primary) Soil Conductivity

Broadway’s soil exhibits a reversed conductivity profile, with the top horizons being the least conductive and the lower horizons significantly more so. The stronger conductivity response at the 60 cm depth during summer suggests that water was being removed from that layer, likely due to a lowering of the groundwater level, causing it to dry out without replenishment from rainfall. This may indicate that groundwater is situated quite close to 60 cm below the surface in this area.

Wybers Wood (Wybers Wood Academy) Soil Conductivity

Wybers Wood’s conductivity profile is much more pronounced, with the 20 cm horizon being highly reactive to rainfall events. The key difference compared to Broadway is that, during summer, the lowest 50/60 cm horizon shows a reduction in conductivity. This is likely due to the proximity of the pond, which began filling with water during this time, leading to infiltration into the lower horizons.

Planter Soil – Soil Moisture

Western Primary School Planter Soil Moisture

Soil moisture data from the planter shows that the 60 cm horizon within the reservoir remains almost constantly dry, with occasional peaks during rainfall events of around 20-25 mm/hr. Unlike the smoother patterns seen in natural soil, the stripey deviation from the average indicates that water primarily accumulates in the top 10 cm during rainfall before filtering downwards. Even in summer, while the top 10 cm was very dry, water was still present in the lower 30/40 cm and did not dry out. Water is not stored for long in the top 10/20 cm, which isn't crucial for a downpipe intervention, but improving storage in the reservoir and using the overflow facility would be more effective.

Wybers Wood Academy Planter Soil Moisture

Wybers Wood soil probe is routinely pulled out by school children which has generated the losses in data. As of October, a new fixing to the probe has been made.

The Wybers Wood planter shows different behaviour, with the 20 cm horizon being the most active and wettest. These differences could be due to the location where water enters the planter or because the plants may have introduced different soil in that area. There are also indications that water is present in the reservoir at the base, with a single peak observed during a 213 mm/hr rainfall event. As monitoring continues into winter 2024, the threshold will be further assessed.

Pilgrim Academy Planter Soil Moisture

Pilgrim Academy's planter was installed during February mid-term.

The Pilgrim Academy planter has a very dry top 10 cm, which reacts to rainfall but consistently maintains a low soil moisture level of around ~5%. The lower 50/60 cm horizons are almost permanently dry, showing no water in the reservoir, except briefly in July. The middle 20/30/40 cm horizons display similar responses to rainfall, with consistent deviations from their averages, and began drying out from mid-May. July rainfall nearly filled the soil to its full retention capacity of around ~40%.

Planter Soil – Soil Conductivity

The soil conductivity within the Wybers Wood planter indicates that the water entering the system is relatively 'clean' and that the soil is quite homogenous. The slight increases in conductivity observed in the 20 cm horizon during summer are likely due to the soil drying out, which concentrates the ions.

Wybers Wood Academy Planter Soil Conductivity

Although the record for conductivity is limited, it clearly shows that the top 10 cm of the Wybers Wood planter became more concentrated over time, primarily as a result of the soil drying out. As moisture levels decreased, the concentration of ions increased, which is typical when water evaporates and leaves behind dissolved salts. This trend is especially notable during drier periods, where reduced infiltration and the drying soil surface lead to a more concentrated conductivity reading. Despite the limited data, this pattern aligns with expectations for soil experiencing seasonal drying.

Pilgrim Academy Planter Soil Conductivity

There are significant spikes in conductivity observed in the top 10 cm of the Wybers Wood planter. These spikes may suggest that the water entering the system is 'dirty,' potentially carrying dissolved materials. However, given the minimal spiking in the lower layers, it could be more indicative of the top 10 cm being in contact with fertiliser or organic compounds, which may have contributed to the conductivity changes.

When comparing this behaviour to natural soils and other planters, where the water sources are generally 'clean,' these observations serve as a useful control. They help to understand how soil conductivity evolves when exposed to different sources of water, such as runoff from highways or other contaminated sources.

Planter Flow

Planters with flow monitoring have been installed at Western Primary, Wybers Wood Academy, Pilgrim Academy, Oasis and Castle Hills. The latter two schools only went online at the end of the hydrological year and data has yet to be collected of significant value. Pilgrim Academy has yet to see flow through the downpipe that is in within the range of the flow meter (ranges shown below). There is one event in which there has been recorded inflow and outflow from the planters indicating that the overflow mechanism of the crates had been used due to the ordinary outflow rate being below the threshold for detection.

Flow meter ranges of measurement

Western Primary School Planter Flow Event

On the 26th May 2024 there was an event in which the inflow and outflow recorded flow. The event corresponds to a peak rainfall of 53.4 mm/hr and a total rainfall depth of 13 mm. That would give a return period of ~2 years for that event.

A measurable volume of 141 litres entered the planter with an outflow being recorded 1.5 hours later which was greater than the standard drainage rate from the planter. Evidence from the soil moisture sensor detected water within the attenuation crate at this time and therefore assumes that the crate overflow was used at this point.

Evidence from planters used at the University of Hull show similar attenuation times ranging from 20 minutes up to 2 hours depending on the event.

Wybers Wood Pond

The Wybers Wood pond drains the school playground and is then pumped out. Two CTD (Conductivity, Temperature and Depth) probes are located at the inlet/outlet and the other in the middle of the pond.

The current pond reached a maximum depth of approximately 40 cm during the hydrological year, coinciding with Storm Henk. Notably, this maximum depth occurred 24 hours after the onset of the storm. The pond has a drainage rate of about 4 cm per day; however, accurate volume calculations would necessitate a survey to estimate its capacity. For most of the year, the middle of the pond retains water or pools, with significant drying typically occurring around June or July.

Wybers Wood Academy Pond Conductivity

Water entering the pond comes from a 'clean' source within the playground, free from highway pollution, which is reflected in the stable water conductivity readings. However, during a cold and icy period in early December, salt was applied to the playground. The first rainfall after this application washed the salt into the pond, resulting in a significant spike in conductivity at the inlet/outlet, reaching up to 10 ds/m—comparable to highly saline water, such as seawater. Since the rainfall amount was low, the salt was not effectively diluted. The conductivity reading for the middle of the pond was approximately 3 ds/m, suggesting that either salt began to leach into the soil or that rainwater within the pond started to dilute the saline concentration.

Going Forward

The next hydrological year will look similar to the current planned installation dates of SuDS in the two council areas.

The next hydrological year highlights include:

- The return to sewer monitoring of Broadway to allow for a post-SuDS survey of performance and a pre-SuDS installation from St Ives Crescent.
- St Ives Crescent instrumentation around water quality and quantity
- Water quality sensor testing to determine their effectiveness in detecting pollution events or bioremediation.
- Clay Lane start with permeable paving, swale and rain garden instrumented.
- Clay Lane sewer monitoring reestablished for winter to determine sewer impact.
- ‘Possible’ start of Castle Hill in terms of engagement and early planning for instrumentation.

UNIVERSITY
of HULL

Energy &
Environment Institute